

Framing school mathematics challenges inside and outside Missouri metropolitan areas

Charles Munter, University of Missouri-Columbia, ✉ munterc@missouri.edu

Phi Nguyen, University of Missouri-Columbia

Cassandra Kinder, University of Missouri-Columbia

We report the results of an interview study conducted with leaders in 50 districts across the U.S. state of Missouri, which focused on what they identified as—and how they framed—their districts’ most salient mathematics-related problems. Our results point to meaningful differences related to whether leaders work within metropolitan areas in terms of the type of problems they identify and how they frame them. Leaders in non-metropolitan districts appear more likely to define and frame problems around improvement in standardized test scores, whereas leaders in metropolitan areas are more likely—though not guaranteed—to define problems in terms of equity and the ways that students experience school mathematics. Related factors include economic resources, mathematics leadership, and commitment to inquiry-based pedagogy.

In our work, we have been interested in initiating partnerships with school districts centered on “problems of practice” (Penuel et al., 2015) related to mathematics. Our efforts have spanned a variety of contexts, from small districts in rural communities to large districts in urban settings. In the course of our initial listening and investigating what such problems of practice might be, we became especially attuned to what district leaders identified as problems and how they framed those problems. As prior work has shown, the problems that leaders identify and how they frame them have consequences—for both policy implementation and the ways that teachers respond (Coburn, 2006). But we also began to wonder whether leaders’ identification and framing of problems varied between different types of communities and settings.

A context of reform

Our study is against a backdrop of “reform” in the U.S. over the last 30 years with respect to both mathematics and broader accountability policies. Regarding the former, there is a strong “school mathematics tradition” (Cobb et al., 1992) of mathematics teachers demonstrating procedures for solving classes of problems, asking students to replicate those procedures,

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and assessing for correctness. For decades, researchers and practitioners in mathematics education have been working to counter the inertia of the school mathematics tradition by describing and enacting teaching that fosters things like inquiry, reasoning, discourse, sense-making, and conceptual understanding (National Council of Teachers of Mathematics [NCTM], 2014).

The common rationale for advocating such a different pedagogical approach is at least twofold. First, it affords the necessary “opportunities to learn” on which research on learning in mathematics classrooms over the years has converged. A second argument is that it affords more equitable opportunities to learn (and fosters more positive experience with) mathematics (NCTM, 2014). Scholars have raised critical questions about the extent to which such “mainstream” equity-oriented practices can disrupt the history of which populations have been best served by school mathematics (e.g., Barajas-López & Larnell, 2019), but they are generally viewed as playing a part in increasing *access* to opportunities to experience success in mathematics—a necessary (though insufficient) condition for equity (Rubel, 2017).

Beyond the few pockets of success that have been achieved in enacting more equitable, high-quality mathematics teaching, the U.S. has been largely unsuccessful in effecting change in how we do school mathematics at scale (Hiebert, 2013). “Reform” language may have made it into circulation, but much of what research in the learning sciences and mathematics education has yielded about supporting mathematics learning has had little real impact or lasting influence in many school settings.

Accountability reforms, on the other hand, *have* been remarkably “successful”—successful in pursuing the broader neoliberal agenda of commodifying access to education (Connell, 2013) through standards and testing policies by which students can be categorized and schools—particularly those serving poor communities of color—can be deemed “failing.” All of this helps to place the blame on teachers and public institutions (and the communities themselves) and to frame market-based reforms as the solution. These reforms have resulted in shifting discourses and building infrastructure around problems manufactured by setting standardized measures of proficiency (Kitchen et al., 2016), perhaps most acutely in mathematics (Pais, 2014).

Because the school mathematics tradition is (seemingly) more amenable to teaching directly to tested procedural proficiencies, many of the responses to accountability pressures run counter to the vision for learning and teaching described above (e.g., NCTM, 2014). This has been especially true—and especially detrimental—in schools serving student populations that are poor and comprised predominantly of African American students or other students of color (Davis & Martin, 2008). Still, those responses structure the current policy climate in which teachers and others work to achieve particular goals—however narrowly defined—for students’ mathematics learning and therefore require our attention if we hope to improve mathematics instruction at a wider scale.

Orienting perspectives

Attending to discourse(s)

Our study is rooted in an assumption that the policy discourses—“language use around a particular socially and historically situated topic, which [...] corresponds to a particular position and perspective”—district leaders employ to define problems and strategies for addressing those problems can be consequential for maintaining or transforming institutional cultures (Bertrand et al., 2015, p. 3). We view the discourses employed by individuals in education institutions—especially those in officially designated positions of leadership—as both reflecting and constructing power relations (Anderson & Mungal, 2015). Whether about mathematics (e.g., the “math wars” and “back to basics” movements) or accountability policies (e.g., proficiency labels for children, “failing” schools), these discourses are drawn and appropriated to varying extents from broader narratives “floating around” in the world (Sfard & Prusak, 2005, p. 18), and are more likely to be taken up when accompanied by public pressure—to which school and district leaders have always been vulnerable. And these discourses help construct well-defined “problems” around which leaders—who certainly do not want to be caught helming “failing” institutions—can chart a clear path toward “improvement.”

Attending to framing

School improvement efforts are (at least implicitly) rooted in the identification of a problem (Penuel et al., 2013). As Stone (1989) explained, problems are defined through *causal stories*, or narratives that actors craft to present certain conditions as (a) caused by human actions and (b) responsive to human intervention. In other words, causal stories define a condition as a problem by placing blame and portraying particular elements of the problem as amenable to policy. Thus, what we are interested in is leaders’ identification and *framing* of problems (Coburn, 2006; Penuel et al., 2013). Scholars have considered how framing as a discursive act can be deployed strategically to influence the perspectives and experiences of others (Benford & Snow, 2000).

In school districts, the discursive frames that leaders deploy to define and motivate action around problems can vary with respect to responses to the current accountability policy climate. In their examination of urban district leaders’ discourses, Jackson et al. (2018) found that leaders’ ways of framing the problem of poor outcomes on state standardized tests often differed depending on their office. Those in leadership offices (responsible for supervising principals) typically employed an instructional *management* frame, which leads to simply reconfiguring human resources in order to produce higher test scores, whereas leaders in curriculum and instruction offices (responsible for teacher support) more likely employed an instructional *improvement* frame, through which they focused on supporting teachers’ learning and growth. Jackson et al.’s (2018) characterization of leaders’ differing frames emerged from particular contexts—leaders from multiple offices within urban districts, framing the problem of poor student outcomes. But there could be other types of problems of interest, and there are certainly other types of districts, including small, rural districts that may not have leaders beyond a superintendent, let alone multiple district offices.

Attending to geography

Location is important because it shapes access to opportunities and resources, conferring “advantages and disadvantages to the persons and organizations whose fortunes are linked to specific places” (Logan, 1978, p. 414). In one of the earliest works investigating the “geography of opportunity” in education, Tate (2008) examined educational outcomes in two places—Dallas and St. Louis—and found that students from low-income neighborhoods were disconnected from the resources associated with the city’s industrial centers. Specific to mathematics education, Tate and Hogrebe (2015) investigated how relationships between poverty, teaching and fiscal contexts, and Algebra I test scores vary between Missouri school districts, finding more statistically significant relationships around the large urban areas.

Methods

Oriented by the previously summarized literature, in this section we describe our methods for answering the following research questions: 1) Do leaders’ identification and framing of problems differ with respect to districts’ size and proximity to metropolitan centers? 2) If so, what factors are related?

Sampling and participants

We conducted our study in Missouri, a state located in the middle of the U.S. and home to more than 6 million people (the country’s 18th most populous). On opposite borders are the state’s two urban centers—Kansas City to the west and St. Louis to the east, with their surrounding metropolitan areas, approximately 2.1 million and 2.8 million people, respectively. At the other end of the density spectrum, about a quarter of the state’s population live in rural communities.

We purposefully sampled a range of districts with respect to population and proximity to metropolitan centers. We classified each Missouri municipality in two ways—by proximity to metropolitan centers and by population size. Table 1 presents the size range and the total and sampled numbers of Missouri municipalities in each of six classifications. Within each classification, we randomly ordered the municipalities and determined the school district the municipality’s residents attended.

Classification	Population range	Total in state	Interviewed
Urban Metro	> 200,000	2	2
Large Metro	25,000 – 200,000	21	11
Small Metro	< 25,000	262	10
Large Non-Metro	25,000 – 200,000	6	5
Small Non-Metro	2,500 – 24,999	93	12
Rural Non-Metro	< 2,500	655	10
Total		1,039	50

Table 1: District sample and classifications.

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In each district, we identified the leader tasked with overseeing mathematics curriculum and instruction. We looked to see whether a district-wide mathematics coordinator was listed on the district's website. If not, we contacted the general curriculum coordinator. If neither such role was listed, we contacted the superintendent. In each case, we asked whether someone else was more directly responsible for mathematics curriculum and instruction. In total, we interviewed 4 superintendents, 17 assistant superintendents of curriculum and instruction (or equivalent), 25 other district leaders in curriculum and instruction (18 of whom were in roles specific to mathematics), and four secondary mathematics teachers. Smaller and/or nonmetro districts were less likely to have mathematics-specific district leaders or, in some cases, even leaders directly responsible for curriculum and instruction.

Data collection

Interviewees participated in semi-structured, 45-minute, audio-recorded interviews. The majority (45) were conducted in 2018, with 5 in 2017. We asked "are there currently any math-related challenges in the district that have been made an explicit focus?" with follow-up questions regarding perceptions of the source of the challenge (or problem) and how the district was currently addressing it. Additionally, we included follow-up probes about any other district mathematics goals, the curriculum in use, and whether a particular instructional approach was being promoted in the district.

To supplement the interview data, we also collected contextual information from governmental websites that could be related to leaders' identification and framing of problems. We collected 2018 data for each district regarding student achievement, student racial and economic demographics, and per-pupil expenditures.

With respect to student achievement, we collected rates of proficiency on federally mandated state standardized tests for grades three through eight. For each district we calculated the percentage of scores categorized as either "proficient" or "advanced" (and not "basic" or "below basic") across all grades combined and subtracted the state average from that percentage. We constructed the variable in this way because we conjectured that concern about achievement (and thus the problems that leaders identify) might be relative to a district's standing compared to other districts.

Similarly, we suspected that leaders' problem identification and framing may be related to or influenced by the economic resources available in the district. As an indicator of that factor, we gathered average 2018 per-pupil expenditures for each district.

Metro and/or larger districts had more racially and ethnically diverse student populations. Besides the two urban metropolitan districts, non-metropolitan districts, on average, had a larger percentage of their student population that qualified for free or reduced-price lunch than their metropolitan counterparts. And yet, per-pupil expenditures were greater, on average, in metropolitan districts.

Analysis

Elsewhere we have described the qualitative analysis through which we categorized what participants identified as mathematics-related problems and how they framed those problems (Munter et al., 2020). In that analysis, we identified three main types of problems described across the 50 interviews: *student outcomes* (e.g., student achievement; n=35), *student experiences* (e.g., enjoyment of mathematics; n=12), and *equity* (e.g., “achievement gaps”; n=3). Expanding Jackson et al.’s (2018) work, we also categorized each leader’s framing as “strictly management,” “strictly learning,” or “both.” In this paper, we focus on our quantitative analysis of the relations between those types and framings of problems and aspects of the leaders’ districts.

As a reminder, our research questions were Do leaders’ identification and framing of problems differ with respect to districts’ size and proximity to metropolitan centers and, if so, what factors are related? Given the dominant discourses nationally about achievement on state standardized tests described previously, we were interested in whether the prevalence of outcomes-related problems compared to other types of problems (i.e., student experiences, equity) varied by geographical region and context. Of course, it is conceivable that leaders in districts whose achievement rates had been significantly below the state average may have been more likely to identify outcomes-related problems than those with higher rates of proficiency. Thus, we employed logistic regression to pursue our questions, as such models are appropriate for dichotomous dependent variables (i.e., outcomes-related problem or other problem) and allowed us to control for districts’ standing in terms of proficiency on the state’s most recent annual standardized test, and to examine possible relations to other factors.

We constructed two sets of models. In the first, we estimated the likelihood of leaders identifying an outcomes-related problem rather than another type of problem. The second set of models estimated the likelihood that leaders employed a strictly management framing of outcomes-related problems. To answer the first research question, for both sets of models, controlling for the district’s difference from the state average in standardized test proficiency rate, we estimated the relation of the dependent variables—problem *type* in the first set of models and problem *framing* in the second—to (a) whether their district was in a metropolitan or non-metropolitan area, and then (b) size of enrollment, with a third model (c) including both to determine which was more strongly related to the type of problem or framing.

For the second research question, we repeated the two sets of models and included three additional contextual variables. As an indicator of districts’ economic resources and support, we included per-pupil expenditures. Motivated by Jackson et al.’s (2018) finding that ways of framing problems can differ with respect to district leaders’ roles, we included a dummy variable for whether districts had an officially designated mathematics leader (who we would have interviewed), as we conjectured that there could be differences related to mathematics specificity of leaders’ foci and backgrounds. Last, we imagined that the extent to which districts were trying to break from the “school mathematics tradition” (Cobb et al., 1992) could influence problem identification and framing. We therefore included a dummy variable

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indicating whether, based on leaders' interview responses, districts were pursuing an instructional vision aligned with an inquiry-oriented approach promoted by reform efforts in mathematics education (e.g., NCTM, 2014) rather than a more conventional, direct instruction approach or no particular approach at all.

Variable	1a	1b	1c	1d	1e
Metropolitan area	-2.20**(0.78)		-1.88*(0.82)	-0.41 (1.05)	
Enrolment (in thousands)		-0.11*(0.05)	-0.06 (0.06)		
Per-pupil expenditures (in thousands)				-0.47 (0.29)	-0.52*(0.25)
District math leader				-2.33*(1.12)	-2.51*(1.05)
Commitment to inquiry-based pedagogy				-2.49*(1.17)	-2.60*(1.13)
Difference from state avg test proficiency	-0.06*(0.03)	-0.07*(0.03)	-0.06*(0.03)	-0.10*(0.05)	-0.11*(0.05)
Constant	2.26***(0.64)	1.87**(0.55)	2.54***(0.70)	8.45*(3.53)	8.96**(3.32)
<i>Pseudo R-squared</i>	0.254	0.307	0.359	0.445	0.442

Table 2: Estimated coefficients (and standard errors) of first set of models predicting an outcomes-related problem ($N = 50$; *** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$).

Results

Tables 2 and 3 list the results of our logistic regression analyses. As shown in Table 2, controlling for percentages of students scoring “proficient” or “advanced” on 2018 state standardized mathematics tests compared to the state average, we found that leaders in metropolitan districts (1a) or larger districts (1b) were less likely to identify outcomes-related problems than were their counterparts in non-metropolitan or smaller districts. Including both variables in the model (1c), however, suggests that metropolitan proximity is more strongly related to the type of problem identified.

Our second set of models (in Table 3) revealed a similar pattern, although it was size (model 2c) that was more strongly related to the dependent variable. Specifically, leaders in smaller districts were more likely to employ a strictly management frame of outcomes-related problems than a strictly learning frame or a combination.

The other models in Tables 2 and 3 attend to our second research question about additional factors. After dropping the now-non-significant metro variable in Model 1d, Model 1e suggests that the identification of outcomes-related problems was negatively related to all of the additional factors, including per-pupil expenditures, whether there was a district math leader, and whether the district was committed to inquiry-based pedagogy.

As Model 2d shows, per-pupil expenditures and math leadership were not related to type of framing of outcomes-related problems. However, the commitment to inquiry-based pedagogy was omitted from this model, because none of the leaders who expressed such a commitment employed a strictly management framing.

Variable	2a	2b	2c	2d
Metropolitan area	-1.978** (0.735)		-1.301 (0.816)	
Enrolment (in thousands)		-0.29* (0.12)	-0.24* (0.12)	-0.25+ (0.14)
Per-pupil expenditures (in thousands)				-0.29 (0.22)
District math leader				-1.22 (1.31)
Difference from state avg test proficiency	-0.019 (0.029)	-0.029 (0.029)	-0.030 (0.033)	-0.04 (0.04)
Constant	0.099 (0.388)	0.675 (0.505)	0.932+ (0.540)	3.98 (2.51)
<i>Pseudo R-squared</i>	0.146	0.232	0.274	0.310

Table 3: Estimated coefficients (and standard errors) of second set of models predicting a strictly management framing of outcomes-related problems ($N = 50$; ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$; + $p < 0.10$).

Discussion

We found that leaders from non-metropolitan districts disproportionately described outcomes-related problems, and that leaders from smaller districts were more likely to employ a strictly “management” framing of those problems. This suggests that in smaller districts geographically beyond the state’s metropolitan centers, discourses of accountability and standardized test achievement predominate when it comes to identifying and framing mathematics challenges. This raises concerns that smaller, non-metro communities may, even more than their larger, metro counterparts, be victims of the “corporate model of schooling,” including orienting school communities to interventionist approaches to raising performance scores that reduce the roles of students and teachers to that of data production and communicating economy-based narratives about the purposes of school (mathematics) (Pais, 2014).

Our investigation of additional factors pointed to possible explanations for the metro-nonmetro difference. That per-pupil expenditures were related to problem type suggests that the very personnel or programs that metro districts can afford may push them to attend to matters beyond accountability expectations. One expenditure in those communities may be district leadership tasked specifically with focusing on mathematics learning and teaching in the district, as our analysis found that the presence of such leaders was related to the type of problem identified. If this is the case, the implications for smaller districts cannot be that they, too, should hire a district mathematics leader, as they likely lack the necessary

resources. Rather, the responsibility lies with those in power—the policy makers and enforcers of the state—to make changes in expectations and/or forms of support to smaller communities outside metro areas in ways that invite emergent local concerns (Chronaki & Lazaridou, 2019) so that issues beyond achievement outcomes are brought into focus.

Our findings also pointed to a relation between districts' commitment to inquiry-based pedagogy and the type and framing of problem identified. That none of the leaders in districts with such a commitment employed a strictly management framing raises concerns that resources devoted to addressing outcomes-related problems—particularly with a strictly management framing—may only perpetuate the “school mathematics tradition” (Cobb et al., 1992) and that this may be especially true in smaller, non-metropolitan communities.

Our findings have important implications for not just state officials and their responsibility to account for the impact of their policies, but also researchers hoping to engage in partnerships with practitioners. Attending to our potential partners' discourses in identifying problems of mutual interest may reveal deeper challenges related to power, geography, and resources.

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